

Faris' Right and Left Hand Rule

Introduction

In **Mechanics**, Dealing with directions of different **Physical Quantities** at a time in a particular situation becomes very difficult sometimes. So, there is a shortcut that can be used to (1) find directions and (2) remember directions in a much simpler way than other methods.

Which Physical Quantities?

The Physical Quantities which are gonna be discussed here is Position Function which is **Base Quantity** in general and its time derivatives up to infinity which are **Derived Quantities** in general.

Octant Symmetry

There is an exact opposite octant for each octant of the 3D Cartesian Coordinate System, say this property of 3D Cartesian Coordinate System as octant symmetry.

Example: Third Octant has x and y negative and z positive and it has an opposite Octant with x and y positive and z negative (Fifth Octant).

Standard

Faris' Right and Left Hand Rule must be exactly opposite, which means there must be an Octant symmetry between Faris' Right and Left Hand Rule.

Example: If Faris' Right Hand Rule has the Third Octant that has x and y negative and z positive then Faris' Left Hand Rule must have an opposite octant with x and y positive and z negative (Fifth Octant).

First Type of Use (Divided Octant Use)

Statement

Open Right or Left Hand by keeping all four fingers straight and thumb at 90 degrees to all four fingers when all fingers and thumb is in same plane now keep the Ring Finger towards palm or in negative y direction. Middle finger direction will align with ring finger. If Thumb is representing reference Direction and Middle Finger is representing direction of $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function then the direction of increasing $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function's $n+1(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function is given by ring finger while the direction of decreasing $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function's $n+1(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function is given by index finger. Middle finger direction can also align with index finger in that case increase and decrease fingers are also exchanged.

For Right Hand

Open Right Hand by keeping all four fingers straight and thumb at 90 degrees to all four fingers when all fingers and thumb is in same plane now keep the Ring Finger towards palm or in negative y direction. Middle finger direction will align with ring finger. If Thumb is representing reference Direction and Middle Finger is representing direction of $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function then the direction of increasing $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function's $n+1(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function is given by ring finger while the direction of decreasing $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function's $n+1(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function is given by index finger. Middle finger direction can also align with index finger in that case increase and decrease fingers are also exchanged.

For Left Hand

Open Left Hand by keeping all four fingers straight and thumb at 90 degrees to all four fingers when all fingers and thumb is in same plane now keep the Ring Finger towards palm or in negative y direction. Middle finger direction will align with ring finger. If Thumb is representing reference Direction and Middle Finger is representing direction of $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function then the direction of increasing $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function's $n+1(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function is given by ring finger while the direction of decreasing $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function's $n+1(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function is given by index finger. Middle finger direction can also align with index finger in that case increase and decrease fingers are also exchanged.

Second Type of Use(Combined Octant Use)

Statement

Open Right or Left Hand by keeping all four fingers straight and thumb at 90 degrees to all four fingers when all fingers and thumb is in same plane now keep the Ring Finger towards palm or in negative y direction. Middle finger direction will align with ring finger. If Thumb is representing reference Direction and Middle Finger is representing direction of $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function then the direction of increasing $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function's $n+1(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function is given by ring finger while the direction of decreasing $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function's $n+1(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function is given by index finger. Middle finger direction can also align with index finger in that case increase and decrease fingers are also exchanged. Rotate Right or Left Hand 180 Degrees in xz Plane for remaining octants of 3D Cartesian Coordinate system.

For Right Hand

Open Right Hand by keeping all four fingers straight and thumb at 90 degrees to all four fingers when all fingers and thumb is in same plane now keep the Ring Finger towards palm or in negative y direction. Middle finger direction will align with ring finger. If Thumb is representing reference Direction and Middle Finger is representing direction of $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function then the direction of increasing $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function's $n+1(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function is given by ring finger while the direction of decreasing $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function's $n+1(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function is given by index finger. Middle finger direction can also align with index finger in that case increase and decrease fingers are also exchanged. Rotate Right Hand 180 Degrees in xz Plane for remaining octants of 3D Cartesian Coordinate system.

For Left Hand

Open Left Hand by keeping all four fingers straight and thumb at 90 degrees to all four fingers when all fingers and thumb is in same plane now keep the Ring Finger towards palm or in negative y direction. Middle finger direction will align with ring finger. If Thumb is representing reference Direction and Middle Finger is representing direction of $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function then the direction of increasing $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function's $n+1(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function is given by ring finger while the direction of decreasing $n(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function's $n+1(\text{th})$ time derivative of position function is given by index finger. Middle finger direction can also align with index finger in that case

increase and decrease fingers are also exchanged. Rotate Left Hand 180 Degrees in xz Plane for remaining octants of 3D Cartesian Coordinate system.

Details

1. Normal Vector

The normal vector to the xy-plane of reference direction (thumb) and n(th) time derivative of position function (middle finger whose direction can align with index or ring finger) can be positive or negative.

2. Reference Direction

Reference Direction is that direction which is considered for help so that the actual direction of the n(th) time derivative of the position function must not be anywhere but only in some specific direction with respect to that reference direction.

3. Right Hand Rule of Cross Product

There can be different orientations of Right Hand Rule of Cross Product. In total 6 orientations of Right Hand Rule of Cross Product exist because there are three positive and three negative directions in which the thumb can point. To define each orientation there are four octants in which two are possible these two are called "Orientation Standards" because two of the octants are equivalent to the other two. I am actually making a standard of right hand rule of cross product by associating each orientation of right hand rule of cross product to octants. There are 6 Orientations of Right Hand Rule of Cross Product each with two orientation standards, so there are 12 Right Hand Rule of Cross Product with respect to orientation standards.

Example:

(1) Consider only one orientation of Right Hand Rule of Cross Product as:

Case 1: If +x axis is curled into +y axis

Case 2: If +y axis is curled into -x axis

Case 3: If -x axis is curled into -y axis

Case 4: If -y axis is curled into +x axis

(2) This orientation of Right hand rule of cross product is called fifth right hand rule of cross product because everytime result is +z axis, if result is +x axis its first, if -x axis its second, if +y axis its third, if -y axis its fourth, if +z axis its fifth and if -z axis its sixth.

(3) Case 1 and Case 3 are equivalent and Case 2 and Case 4 are also equivalent so only two octants are valid for each orientation of Right Hand Rule of cross Product.

(4) The first cases (here Case 1 and Case 2) will become orientation standards of this orientation of Right Hand Rule of Cross Product. First orientation standard is called A Orientation Standard and second one as B orientation standard. The Octant number will tell which case is first (A Orientation Standard) and which is second (B Orientation Standard) for every orientation of right hand rule of cross product.

Fifth Right Hand Rule of Cross Product

The Fifth Orientation of the Right Hand Rule of Cross Product called Fifth Right Hand Rule of Cross Product (5th RCP) which can be defined as:

Fifth Right Hand Rule of Cross Product's A Orientation Standard (5th RCP's A-OS): Curl fingers from +x axis into +y axis then thumb will show direction of +z axis.

Fifth Right Hand Rule of Cross Product's B Orientation Standard: Curl fingers from +y axis to -x axis and thumb will point in +z axis.

1. In Linear Mechanics

Reference Line Prove

I am given a cartesian coordinate system which include vectors \mathbf{n} (normal vector), \mathbf{r} (reference line vector, explained afterwards) and $\mathbf{r}^{(n)}(t)$ (position function's n (th) time derivative) and there negative vectors also. This is the cartesian coordinate system formed by plane including thumb and middle finger and the considered normal vector perpendicular to plane. In Faris' Right Hand Rule only Octant 1, Octant 4, Octant 5 and Octant 8 can be made by thumb, middle finger and normal vector. In Faris' Left Hand Rule only Octant 2, Octant 3, Octant 6 and Octant 7 can be made by thumb, middle finger and normal vector. These octants which include vectors are called initial octants and the cross product of vectors in each octant is like this $\mathbf{x} \times \mathbf{y}$, $\mathbf{y} \times \mathbf{z}$ and $\mathbf{z} \times \mathbf{x}$ the answer to these will give a resultant octant. I have to apply each orientation of Right Hand Rule with its Orientation Standards to all Octants. $12 \text{ right hand rule of cross products with orientation standards} \times 8 \text{ octants} = 96 \text{ Cases}$.

For the prove of reference line direction's Second Condition (given below) I have applied Fifth Right Hand Rule of Cross Product's A Orientation standard to Octant 1 in Faris' Right Hand Rule and to Octant 7 in Faris' Left Hand Rule, note that both octants are opposite due to need of Octant Symmetry as a standard between Left and Right Hand. I have solved two cases below in this way.

1. First Type of Use

For Right Hand.

Reference Direction

Reference Direction is a direction of a line called **Reference Line**.

Reference Line Direction

(1) It is considered perpendicular to the direction of motion.

(2) The reference line is considered toward the positive x axis.

Prove

The Prove of the two conditions of Reference Line Direction is:

(1) An angle of 90 degree from the reference line to the direction of motion always exists due to the definition of Reference Direction (here reference line) that is chosen so that the position function's n (th) time derivative must be in some specific direction with respect to reference direction.

(2) Right Hand Rule of Cross Product

Octant 1 (On which 5th RCP's A-OS is applied)

Vector Equation

$$\mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{r}^{(n)}(t) = \mathbf{n} = r r^{(n)}(t) \sin\theta \hat{\mathbf{A}}$$

$$\mathbf{r}^{(n)}(t) \times \mathbf{n} = \mathbf{r} = n r^{(n)}(t) \sin\theta \hat{\mathbf{A}}$$

$$\mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}^{(n)}(t) = n r \sin\theta \hat{\mathbf{A}}$$

Prove

$$\mathbf{i} \times \mathbf{j} = \mathbf{k}$$

$$\mathbf{j} \times \mathbf{k} = \mathbf{i}$$

$$\mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{i} = \mathbf{j}$$

Combined Scalar Triple Product Equation

$$\mathbf{r} \cdot (\mathbf{r}^n(t) \times \mathbf{n}) = |r|^2$$

Octant 1 (On which 6th RCP's A-OS is applied)

Vector Equation

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{r}^n(t) \times \mathbf{r} &= -\mathbf{n} = -r r^n(t) \sin\theta \hat{A} \\ \mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{n} &= -\mathbf{r}^n(t) = -n r \sin\theta \hat{A} \\ \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{r}^n(t) &= -\mathbf{r} = -n r^n(t) \sin\theta \hat{A} \end{aligned}$$

Prove

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{j} \times \mathbf{i} &= -\mathbf{k} \\ \mathbf{i} \times \mathbf{k} &= -\mathbf{j} \\ \mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{j} &= -\mathbf{i} \end{aligned}$$

Combined Scalar Triple Product Equation

$$\mathbf{r}^n(t) \cdot (\mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{n}) = -|r^n(t)|^2$$

For Left Hand

Reference Direction

Reference Direction is a direction of a line called **Reference Line**.

Reference Line Direction

(1) It is considered perpendicular to the direction of motion.

(2) The reference line is considered toward the negative x axis.

Prove

The Prove of the two conditions of Reference Line Direction is:

(1) An angle of 90 degree from the reference line to the direction of motion always exists due to the definition of Reference Direction (here reference line) that is chosen so that the position function's n(th) time derivative must be in some specific direction with respect to reference direction.

(2) **Right Hand Rule Of Cross Product**

Octant 7 (On which 5th RCP's A-OS is applied)

Vector Equation

$$\begin{aligned} -\mathbf{r} \times -\mathbf{r}^n(t) &= \mathbf{n} = r r^n(t) \sin\theta \hat{A} \\ -\mathbf{r}^n(t) \times -\mathbf{n} &= \mathbf{r} = n r^n(t) \sin\theta \hat{A} \\ -\mathbf{n} \times -\mathbf{r} &= \mathbf{r}^n(t) = n r \sin\theta \hat{A} \end{aligned}$$

Prove

$$\begin{aligned} -\mathbf{i} \times -\mathbf{j} &= \mathbf{k} \\ -\mathbf{j} \times -\mathbf{k} &= \mathbf{i} \\ -\mathbf{k} \times -\mathbf{i} &= \mathbf{j} \end{aligned}$$

Combined Scalar Triple Product Equation

$$\mathbf{r} \cdot (\mathbf{r}^n(t) \times \mathbf{n}) = |r|^2$$

Octant 7 (By 6th RCP's A-OS is applied)

Vector Equation

$$\begin{aligned} -\mathbf{r}^n(t) \times -\mathbf{r} &= -\mathbf{n} = -r r^n(t) \sin\theta \hat{A} \\ -\mathbf{r} \times -\mathbf{n} &= -\mathbf{r}^n(t) = -n r \sin\theta \hat{A} \end{aligned}$$

$$-\mathbf{n} \times -\mathbf{r}^n(t) = -\mathbf{r} = -n r^n(t) \sin\theta \hat{A}$$

Prove

$$-\mathbf{j} \times -\mathbf{i} = -\mathbf{k}$$

$$-\mathbf{i} \times -\mathbf{k} = -\mathbf{j}$$

$$-\mathbf{k} \times -\mathbf{j} = -\mathbf{i}$$

Combined Scalar Triple Product Equation

$$\mathbf{r}^n(t) \cdot (\mathbf{r} \times \mathbf{n}) = -|r^n(t)|^2$$

Details

If one compares the proof of reference line direction's second condition in Faris' Right and Left Hand Rule, Octant Symmetry is seen. I have applied 5th RCP's A-OS to Octant 1 and Octant 7 for Octant Symmetry between Faris' Right and Left Hand Rule. The scalar triple product equation is same because of Octant Symmetry and that is why the Octant symmetry is needed to not only make a difference between Right and Left hand but also for same Scalar triple product equation. If the octant symmetry is not present and octants are same then scalar triple product cannot also make a difference between right and left hand so Octant symmetry is important and in case of entirely different octants between right and left hand again it will be difficult to make a difference between right and left hand and mathematically scalar triple product equation will be random of right and left hand which is wrong since some standard must be considered.

2. Second Type of Use

In this way the only difference is that Faris' Right Hand Rule can be used as Faris' Left Hand Rule by rotating Right Hand 180 Degrees in xz Plane and after rotation the Octant Symmetry Correction must be added means the two fingers of initial octant in hand must be exactly opposite in Faris' Right Hand rule and 180 degrees shifted Faris' Right hand rule to preserve the Standard of Octant symmetry between Faris' Right Hand Rule and 180 degree shifted Faris' Right Hand Rule. Similarly Faris' Left Hand Rule can also be used and its 180 degree shifted version.

2. In Angular Mechanics

Scene View

The scene of movement (rotatory or circular motion) of any body around an axis shifts direction after each 180 degrees.

Example: When a ball is undergoing circular motion around a fixed axis its direction of circular motion changes from positive x axis to negative x axis after each 180 degrees.

Scene View Arrow

Positive scene View Arrow: If a body is moving (rotatory or circular motion) from left to right in the positive x axis an arrow must be drawn to show a positive scene view called positive scene view arrow.

Negative Scene View Arrow: When a body shifts after 180 degrees and starts moving to the left in the negative x axis from right an arrow must be drawn to show a negative scene view called negative scene view arrow.

1. First Type of Use

Reference Direction

Reference Direction is the Direction of Rotation.

For Clockwise Movement

Faris' Right Hand Rule changes to Faris' Left Hand Rule after 180 degrees in clockwise movement.

For Anticlockwise Movement

Faris' Left Hand Rule changes to Faris' Right Hand Rule after 180 degrees in anticlockwise movement.

2.Second Type of Use

Reference Direction

Reference Direction is the Direction of Rotation.

For Clockwise Movement

Rotate Faris' Right Hand Rule 180 Degrees in xz Plane after the body's 180 degrees angular displacement movement and it becomes 180 degrees shifted Faris' Right Hand Rule.

Or

Rotate 180 degrees shifted Faris' Left Hand Rule in xz Plane after the body's 180 degrees angular displacement movement and it becomes Faris' Left Hand Rule.

(For One Rotation)

For Anticlockwise Movement

Rotate 180 Degrees shifted Faris' Right Hand Rule in xz Plane after the body's 180 degrees angular displacement movement and it becomes Faris' Right Hand Rule.

Or

Rotate Faris' Left Hand Rule in xz Plane after the body's 180 degrees angular displacement movement and it becomes 180 degrees shifted Faris' Left Hand Rule.

(For One Rotation)

Details

1.Notes

1.Octant Symmetry Correction must be added to preserve the Standard of Octant symmetry between Faris' Right Hand Rule and 180 degree shifted Faris' Right Hand Rule.Same for Faris' Left Hand Rule.Octant Symmetry Correction means if in Faris' Right Hand Rule Octant 1 is considered then in its 180 degrees shifted version middle finger will align with ring finger to make it Octant 7.

2.In First Type of Use 3D cartesian coordinate system is divided among Faris' Right and Left Hand Rule.In Second Type of Use hand is shifted 180 degrees so that both hands can separately serve as a 3D Cartesian Coordinate system.

2.A Technical Problem

To apply each orientation of the Right hand rule of cross product with its orientation standards to all octants a problem is encountered if an orientation standard is with respect to some octant how it is possible to apply it to other octants except right hand rule's standard octant.

The Solution

This problem can be solved by the Octant Change Method and Free Movement Method.

Octant Change Method

In this method initial octant vectors are shifted through octants to match with axes of Nth RCP's A/B-OS octant which is fixed.

Example

Suppose 5th RCP's A-OS is applied to a given Octant 2 called initial octant which has vectors. In this method 5th RCP's A-OS Hand is fixed and initial octant vectors are moved.

Octant 2 → Octant 7 → Octant 8 → Octant 5
 -x → -x -x → -x +x → +z +x → +z
 +y → +y -y → +y -y → +y +y → -x
 +z → +z -z → +z -z → -x -z → +y

To make things easy one can write this as

Initial Octant → x×y (Octant 7) → y×z (Octant 8) → z×x (Octant 5)
 0 degree → -180 degrees y and z axis shift → +180 degrees x axis shift → +180 degrees y axis shift

Considering y axis not being shifted as first it goes +180 degrees and then -180 degrees it gives 0 degree. Where x and z is +180 degrees and -180 degrees shifted respectively. + and - is - so the resultant axes will be exactly opposite to the initial one which is Octant 8.

The octant vectors are tilted to Octant 7 axes for x×y then to Octant 8 for y×z and finally to Octant 5 for z×x. The answer of these cross products can also be found out by unit vectors and resultant octant or final octant will be obtained.

Free Movement Method

In this method orientation standard hand can move to find out the cross product's Resultant octant between the vectors of the initial octant.

Example:

Again Suppose 5th RCP's A-OS is applied to a given Octant 2 called initial octant. In this Method initial Octant axes are fixed and 5th RCP's A-OS hand is moved freely to align with octant and get x×y, y×z and z×x here thumb will show direction of resultant octant axes which is Octant 8.

Note

Both of the methods are equivalent because in one method axes are fixed and the hand is moved (Free movement method) while in other method hand is fixed and axes are moved (Octant Change Method). It is more appropriate to use Octant Change Method because Free movement method is although correct but it mostly cause to change the orientation of right hand rule of cross product which is wrong since correct orientation is demanded by rules but physically insignificant.

3. Visualizing all 96 Cases

Writing a simple equation of all 96 cases as

$$[\pm r, \pm r^n(t), \pm n] = \pm |N|^2 \text{ Where } |N| = |r| \text{ or } |r^n(t)| \text{ or } |n|$$

(1) I am given 8 octants for each of the six orientations of the right hand rule of cross product. The vectors in octant can be written as a Scalar triple product and then adding ± with them is good to encounter all 8 octants.

(2) The factor still remains is to encounter only now 12 right hand rule of cross product in the equation so I notice in every right hand rule of cross product there is only arrangement difference of writing vectors in triple scalar product equation, sometimes 'r^n(t)' occurs first in

the scalar triple product equation and sometimes 'n' first so a simple scalar triple product equation that I mentioned can be changed by changing the vector's position.

(3) Now the two octant axes signs that are associated with each orientation of the right hand rule of the cross product does not matter because the actual cross product is between vectors and their signs in a given octant.

(4) For the two octants of each orientation of the right hand rule of cross product only resultant octant arrangement with all 8 given initial octants become different so only arrangement of initial resultant octant pairs becomes different for orientation standards of each right hand rule of cross product and for all six right hand rules of cross product only axes vectors cross products changes because sometimes there is $x \times y (r \times r^n(t))$, $y \times z (r^n(t) \times n)$ and $z \times x (n \times r)$ or $[r, r^n(t), n]$ and in any other right hand rule of cross product only cross product direction changes as $y \times x (r^n(t) \times r)$, $x \times z (r \times n)$ and $z \times y (n \times r^n(t))$ or $[r^n(t), r, n]$.

4. Prove

Consider $n=1$ now the Middle finger quantity is Angular velocity while Ring and Index finger quantity is Angular acceleration. Now use Faris' Right Hand Rule in this way:

"Open Right Hand by keeping all four fingers straight and thumb at 90 degrees to all four fingers when all fingers and thumb is in same plane now keep the Ring Finger towards palm or in negative y direction. Middle finger direction will align with ring finger. If Thumb is representing rotation Direction and Middle Finger is representing direction of angular velocity then the direction of increasing angular velocity's angular acceleration is given by ring finger while the direction of decreasing angular velocity's angular acceleration is given by index finger. Middle finger direction can also align with index finger in that case increase and decrease fingers are also exchanged. Rotate Right Hand after 180 Degrees of angular displacement in xz Plane for remaining octants of 3D Cartesian Coordinate system."

To prove whether Faris' Right Hand Rule predicts the accurate direction or not follow these steps:

First Step

Develop a situation.

For Example: Consider a long object undergoing rotatory motion and at its one end point there is an axis of rotation at other end a point P is considered which is going circular motion if it is separated now both point P and object under rotation has positive scene view arrow in clockwise movement and direction of Angular Velocity toward axis of rotation by Right Hand Rule.

Second Step

Use the Equation.

For Example: In Same Example, According to the following equation:

$$\alpha = d\omega / dt$$

If Angular Velocity is increasing then positive sign in equation shows direction of Angular Acceleration which is in same direction as Angular Velocity while if Angular Velocity is decreasing the negative sign in equation shows the direction of Angular Acceleration is in the opposite direction of Angular Velocity.

Third Step

Combine the first two steps in first step proof of thumb and middle finger quantities direction is presented while in second step proof of ring and index finger quantities direction proof is presented which combinedly gives the proof of Faris' Right Hand Rule in this case.

Note

Now this can be generalized to n time derivatives and other octants also.

5. Multiple times Use

In situations where Faris' Right and Left Hand Rule is used multiple times it can sometimes cause confusion. So for clarification a situation is considered. Let's suppose a body's linear velocity is decreasing and direction of linear jerk is needed. If it is known whether linear acceleration is decreasing or not then linear jerk direction can be found as Ring Finger shows direction of decreasing linear velocity's linear acceleration simply point your Middle Finger toward ring finger direction and now the direction of increasing linear acceleration's linear jerk is shown by Index Finger while the direction of decreasing linear acceleration's linear jerk is shown by Ring Finger. Considering Octant one initially.

6. Two Special cases

1. Angular Displacement can be treated as a vector only when it is very small.
2. As n increases for time derivatives, position function time derivative quantity lost its practical meaning while still having theoretical importance.
(So these can be regarded as a limitation of Faris' Right and Left Hand Rule).

7. Benefits

If this Rule is established then:

1. It will make it easy to remember directions.
2. It will make it easy to find some unknown directions.